

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE USE OF MODERN MANAGEMENT METHODS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF HOUSING STOCK IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article provides suggestions and recommendations on the use of modern management methods in order to improve the management of the housing stock of our republic.

Key words: housing stock management, cost-effective production, cost-effective technologies, process optimization, innovation, innovative approach, quality of services.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada respublikamiz uy-joy fondini boshqarishni takomillashtirishda zamonaviy menejment usullaridan foydalanish yo'llari borasida taklif va tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: uy-joy fondini boshqarish, tejamkor ishlab chiqarish, tejamkor texnologiyalar, jarayonlarni optimallashtirish, innovatsiya, innovatsion yondashuv, xizmatlar sifati.

Аннотация: В данной статье приводятся предложения и рекомендации по использованию современных методов управления в целях совершенствования управления жилищным фондом нашей республики.

Ключевые слова: управление жилищным фондом, рентабельное производство, рентабельные технологии, оптимизация процессов, инновации, инновационный подход, качество услуг.

INTRODUCTION

In digital economic development, the result of the innovation process and innovation activity is one of the most important factors that determine the development of the national economy of any country and determine its competitiveness in the global market. In the current period, economic growth and development will be provided in the same place, whichever enterprise, network, territory or country as a whole, innovation management activities are well established in the economy.

But the practice shows that without a sufficient emphasis on innovation in management, enterprises, industries, regions and the national economy as a whole associate the development mainly with technical and tech-

nological innovations. But management efficiency cannot be achieved only if you know how to introduce new equipment and techniques into practice. In our opinion, the introduction of a system of effective use of modern management methods and technologies is no less significant [3].

The renewal and development of any activity occurs first of all at the expense of improving the methods of its implementation. Therefore, the need arises to introduce innovative conceptual approaches aimed at improving the management system that determines the innovation strategy of any activity. One of the modern ways to improve control efficiency and improve its performance is the introduction of the Lean Production (cost-effective production) concept. Most successful companies in the world market are showing their achievements and cases with the effectiveness of this approach [4].

Despite the fact that in recent years the method of economical production has been widely used and popularized in leading foreign countries, in our republic it can be said that the use of this method of management is not in demand or if it is not at all imagined by most enterprises and organizations.

METHODOLOGY

The Lean Production (cost-effective production) concept is based on the management principles of the Japanese company Toyota (Toyota), the essence of which is to eliminate all types of losses, that is, the main idea in this is to maximize the simplification of the organization of production and eliminate losses.

The term Lean Production first appeared on March 1, 1988, following an article by John Kraftsiku titled Lean Manufacturing celebration(triumphi) based on his research work at the Massachusetts University of Technology. At work, he relied on his own work experience as a quality engineer at the Toyota company division in California [5].

The cost-effective production method is an innovative approach that demonstrates quality management aimed at optimizing production processes in itself, reducing costs, improving product quality, satisfying consumer preferences [6].

To introduce cost-effective production, it is necessary to understand the content of the principles of this system, which are manifested in the following [3]:

- determination of the creator of product value from the point of view of the final consumer(knowing exactly what is needed for the consumer);
- determination of all necessary behaviors in the product production and loss elimination chain (sequential interpretation of all behaviors in the process from the receipt of the order to the delivery of the product to the final consumer);
- restructuring behavior in the production chain so that they themselves show the flow of affairs(lack of expectations, interruptions and other losses);
- behavior that will be necessary for the final consumer (do only what the final consumer needs);
- striving for perfection at the expense of constant reduction of unnecessary behavior(constant improvement of work at the expense of finding and eliminating losses).

It can be noted separately that in any organization there may be a large amount of losses that lead to a decrease in the efficiency of affairs and do not cause any harm to the final consumer.

In general, "cost-effective production" manifests itself in the optimization of business processes to attract all employees and to the maximum extent to target the market.

Examples of the most popular and widely used supports of modern economical production are 5s, Andon, Kaizen, Muda, PDCA and others.

Sometimes, in order to comprehend the concept in a holistic way, the name of one of the elements of this system is used "JIT" (Just-in-time, "clearly – in - time-production"), "Kaydzen" [7].

Another famous American Scientist - consultant in the theory of quality management is E. Deming(1900-1993.) Actively promoted the Schuchart cycle, and later modified the PDCA cycle to PDSA ("study" - study), and made an important contribution to the creation of the Kaidzen system in Japan in the 50s of the last century, proposing its use.

Kaydzen (jap. 改善; kaydzen; Kaizen this is a Japanese philosophy or practice aimed at continuously improving production processes, developments, auxiliary business processes and management, as well as all aspects of life. Its meaning in translation from Japanese means "continuous improvement" or "changes for the better" [8]. In general, the goal of kaydzen is lossless production.

A from CIS scientists who made a significant contribution to solving problems in the reform and management of Housing and communal services. Abolina, E. Byakov, B. Gongolo, E. Dobroves, A. Dronova, G. Ivanova,

L.Konyukhova, A.Kruglikova, O.Lavrukhina, N.Maksimov, L.It is possible to cite the names of Chernyshov and others. Theoretical and practical aspects of the field of Housing and communal services in Uzbekistan I.Davletov, T.Khasanov, V.Yadavov, D.Embodied in the scientific work of all of them and others. But until now, scientific research has not been carried out in our republic on the introduction of the method of economical production into the field of communal housing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the research process carried out to write our scientific article, methods of scientific observation, abstract-logical thinking, comparative and systematic analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, induction and deduction were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is known that in the national economy of Uzbekistan, material production in more than a hundred different directions manifests itself in the network and sub-network networks and service sectors. One such area is the housing and communal services sector. Expressed in scientific language, housing and communal services is a network complex that provides for the functioning of various engineering infrastructures of settlement structures through the provision of a wide range of housing services for people and their living, such as water supply, water supply, overhaul services for houses and others [9].

This area plays an important role in the socio-economic development of our republic because the future development of the country's economy is closely related to the increase in the standard of living of the population, which means that the development of the housing and communal sector and the improvement of the living conditions of the population. This area serves to provide the housing and communal services of the population and the needs of industrial enterprises for production resources.

Ensuring the well-being of the population, creating the necessary conditions for their good survival is the ultimate goal of the reforms carried out in our republic. In such a way that the effective functioning of the housing and communal sphere is important in this regard, the effective introduction of modern management mechanisms that justify themselves in the practice of developed countries of Industry Management and regulation, in turn, has a positive effect on increasing the standard of living of the population. But so far, the quality of work in the field does not fully meet the requirements of today's era. In particular, it can be noted that the quality of services provided by utilities, as well as the use of resource-intensive and energy-intensive technologies in the field, is not at the level of demand, despite the fact that there is a constant trend of increasing the cost of utility payments paid by the population.

The application of innovative methods and approaches to increasing the level of scientific management of resources is becoming more important today [3]. It is not accidental that this is one of the most important reserves of increasing labor productivity in housing and communal services. Resource and reserve management-hence, from an innovative point of view, is the effective use of electricity, heat, gas resources, labor resources in housing and communal services, etc., taking into account social needs.

From the above points, we believe that the main focus today should be on innovation development in order to improve the housing and communal services market. It is the innovation that makes it possible to objectively reflect on the current state of management activity and the realities that the problems in it have arisen in the field of reforming housing and communal services.

Despite the high rate of population growth in Uzbekistan in the last few decades (growth in the years of independence was 9.4 million more than a person), there is a steady increase in the residential population. This is despite the fact that over the past period the population has steadily increased the level of housing the population per person in 2011 to 15 sq.m of the total area per person, where m corresponds, in 2017 this figure is 15.4 sq.m up to m, and in 2023-18.5 sq.m. [12] (Figure 1).

The state of decline of Housing has become one of the most pressing problems of the state today. It mainly consists of issues such as the obsolescence of housing funds, the formation of tariffs for services provided, violations of the obligations of managing companies to the population, the implementation of current and capital repairs in a timely manner, the relocation of the population from accident housing [3].

An effective system of monitoring the maintenance of a multi-family housing fund at the appropriate level has not been established, in many cases the specified requirements for the technical exploitation of a housing fund and the safe survival of the population in it are allowed to be violated. The rules and deadlines for the implementation of repair and restoration work of buildings and structures are not observed, work is not carried out on the demolition of old houses, the state of areas adjacent to multi-apartment houses does not fully meet sanitary norms, rules and hygiene standards. The population is not adequately supplied with quality drinking water and centralized Heat Supply.

Figure 1: For the period 2011-2023, the population was provided with housing (1 housing area per inhabitant m²).

Moreover, despite the fact that in recent years consistent efforts have been made towards the formation of a modern market for utilities in our country, the analysis shows that a number of laws adopted in the past period do not fully provide the legal basis for the development of the industry.

From this point of view, taking into account the fact that the cost-effective production concept, which is effectively used in the practice of advanced foreign countries today, is an innovative approach that demonstrates modern quality management aimed at optimizing production processes, reducing costs, improving product quality, satisfying consumer desires, we consider it worthwhile to apply this method in the field of management.

In order to correctly adapt cost-effective technologies in the field of Housing and communal services, it is important to distinguish the following aspects of the processes themselves in this field of Service:

- the importance of information and the fact that these information is complete, understandable and reliable;
- perceptual level variety of tasks;
- numerous stages of information transmission;
- hidden benefits and losses from providing effective services;
- lack of clear motivation to accelerate the provision of services ^[10].

Estimates suggest that 30 percent to 50 percent of spending in service organizations are costs resulting from lower rates of consumer desire satisfaction or processing ^[11].

According to the analyzes, the problems accumulated in the field of Housing and communal services of our republic today can be systematized as follows:

- dominance of administrative methods in relation to economic methods of Management in the field;
- high expenditure in business, high level of energy and resource loss in the process of production and provision of services;
- lack of transparency in the formation of tariffs;
- the fact that population awareness is not in the line of demand in terms of expenditure;
- low investment attractiveness of industry organizations;
- high proportion of people who do not pay utility bills on time among residents who have the opportunity to pay utility bills on time;

- to maximize the simplification of the organization of the housing and communal services system and eliminate excessive spending, as well as to ensure more service at lower intervals;
- formation of a systematic approach to the organization of services to the population in the field of Housing and communal services, which includes its quality control;
- ensuring the development of innovative methods in the field and creating the maximum possible consumer value for investors by introducing modern innovation and information technology into the service sector;
- to establish a cost-effective production(service) system based on the principle of “at the exact deadline with the lowest costs” in the repair of the housing stock.

Based on the above comments, we conclude that the successful introduction of the concept of cost-effective production, which is effectively used in the practice of sectors and sectors of advanced foreign countries, into the activities of farms of our republic’s communal services economy, in particular the housing stock management system, can make an important contribution to improving the efficiency of reforms carried out in the system.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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